

SPONTANEOUS CRYSTALLISATION FROM SUPERSATURATED META-STABLE SOLUTIONS

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The supersolubility range $T_s - T_c$ for inorganic salts follows closely the nature of the solubility curves. For substances whose temperature coefficient of solubility is constant throughout the range from 0° to 100°, the value of $T_s - T_c$ is constant at different temperatures. A change in the temperature coefficient of solubility denotes also a change in the value of the limit of supersaturation. Substances like $KClO_4$, NH_4Cl and $PbAc_2$, which have meta-stable regions in their normal solubility range, display tendency to stabilisation against spontaneous crystallisation, if heated beyond the meta-stable region and cooled. Saturated solutions of hydrates, which have transition temperatures and dissolve in their water of crystallisation on heating, maintain high supersolubility and stabilise against spontaneous crystallisation on heating and cooling possibly due to high solubility of the less hydrated species at low temperatures.

Miers and Issac (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 413) demonstrated that if aqueous solutions of salts were cooled and *kept continuously shaken*, at a particular temperature, a copious shower of minute crystals appeared throughout the solution. This phenomenon occurred at quite different temperatures for each solution according to their strength. This temperature is identified as that at which spontaneous crystallisation begins in supersaturated solutions. The author (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 60) has shown that the condition for spontaneous crystallisation on supercooling in the meta-stable region is dependent on the particle size of the solute in equilibrium with the saturated solution and has drawn conclusion that the substances like copper sulphate, sodium thiosulphate will exhibit high supersolubility on cooling, but those like sodium chloride and barium chloride will show greater tendency for spontaneous crystallisation than maintaining supersolubility. The minimum size of particle for spontaneous crystallisation has been shown to be $50\mu\mu$. But in most supersaturated solutions experimented upon, the adjustment of uniform sizing of particles, from which the supersaturated solutions are to be made, is a matter of considerable practical difficulty. In practice therefore, saturated solutions made at any temperature, if cooled without crystallisation, are considered supersaturated at the lower temperatures and $T_s - T_c$ (where T_s is the temperature of saturation and T_c , the temperature where crystallisation begins) as the regions at which supersaturation exists in the meta-stable state. It is the object of this investigation to study the behaviour of different substances in this region at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used in this investigation were highly pure, being either o Merck or Khalbaum. The water for preparing solutions was distilled five times over in Pyrex vessels and stored in Jena glass bottles.

TABLE I

T_s	$T_s - T_c$	Average $T_s - T_c$	
	1. Potassium chloride.		
40	12.6 (54) ; 12.8 (65)	12.7	
50	13.3 (65)	13.3	
60	13.0 (62) ; 13.4 (62) ; 13.2 (72)	13.2	
70	13.0 (72) ; 13.6 (90)	13.3	13.1
	2. Potassium nitrate.		
	A		
10	3.8 (15)	3.8	
20	3.8 (25) ; 3.4 (25)	3.6	
30	4.4 (31) ; 4.6 (31)	4.5	3.9
	B		
40	7.8 (42)	7.8	
50	7.8 (52) ; 7.8 (52) ; 7.8 (55)	7.8	
60	7.2 (62) ; 7.9 (62)	7.6	
70	8.0 (71) ; 8.0 (72) ; 8.0 (72)	8.0	7.8
	3. Boric acid.		
	A		
10	6.0 (17) ; 6.1 (25)	6.1	
20	6.0 (28) ; 6.4 (28)	6.2	
30	6.8 (36)	6.8	6.4
	B		
40	7.6 (45) ; 7.8 (55)	7.7	7.7
	C		
50	10.0 (65) ; 10.0 (75) ; 10.2 (85)	10.1	
60	10.2 (65) ; 10.6 (75) ; 10.6 (85) ; 10.4 (95) ; 10.4 (95)	10.5	10.3
	D		
70	12.2 (72) ; 12.5 (85) ; 13.0 (95)	12.8	12.8
	4. Potassium perchlorate.		
	A		
10	6.2 (15)	6.2	6.2
	B		
20	2.6 (45) ; 2.6 (60)	2.6	
40	2.6 (45)	2.6	
50	2.6 (52) ; 2.4 (65) ; 2.4 (75) ; 2.1 (85)	2.4	
60	2.2 (65) ; 2.0 (65)	2.1	2.4
	C		
70	No supersaturation ; within 0.1° below the temperatures		
80	there is a shower of crystals.		

TABLE I (contd.)

T_s	$T_s - T_c$	Average $T_s - T_c$	
5. Ammonium chloride.			
A			
10	3.4 (12) ; 3.4 (30) ; 3.8 (50)	3.5	
20	3.8 (22) ; 3.8 (52) ; 4.0 (35)	3.8	
30	3.6 (33) ; 4.0 (60)	3.5	
40	3.4 (43) ; 3.6 (43) ; 3.6 (43)	3.8	3.7
A ₁			
	7.6 (55) ; 7.9 (65)	7.8	7.8
B			
50	5.2 (54)	5.2	
60	5.2 (62) ; 5.4 (62)	5.3	5.3
B ₁			
50	9.0 (65) ; 10 (77)	9.5	9.5
C			
70	6.0 (72) ; 6.8 (71) ; 6.4 (71)	6.4	6.4
(N. B. In the last case the shower of crystals was meagre)			
6. Sodium thiosulphate.			
10	No crystallisation till 0° (11) ; 25 (70).		
7. Potash alum.			
10	5 (15) ; 5 (15) ; Nil (30, till -5°)		
20	17 (24) ; Nil (40) till -6°C.		
30	26.2 (35) ; 28.0 (30) ; Nil till -7 (61)		
40	38.0 (42) ; 37.6 (43) ; Nil till -7 (61)		
50	40.0 (52) ; Nil till -7 (70)		
60	38.0 (63) ; 38.5 (63) ; Nil till -8 (70)		
8. Lead acetate.			
A			
10	8.4 (42)	8.4	
20	8.0 (24) ; 8.0 (24) ; 8.2 (40)	8.1	8.3
A ₁			
	26.6 (60)		
B			
30	15.5 (31) ; 14.5 (32)	15.0	
B ₁			
	21.0 (50) ; 20.0 (60)		
40	15.0 (42) ; 15.0 (42)	15.0	15.0
	23.5 (62)		
C			
50	33.0 (52) ; 33.0 (51) ; 33.5 (51)	33.2	33.2

The figures in parenthesis indicate the highest temperatures to which the solutions were heated above T_s in each case.

The apparatus used was a small bulb, like that of the specific gravity bottle, about 7.5 c.c. in capacity with a well ground-in stopper. The above distilled water (5 c.c.) was taken in the bulb. The substance to be examined was weighed out carefully, according to its solubility, in 5 c.c. at the temperature of the experiment. The solubility data from the International Critical Tables were taken. The bulb was stoppered and hung in a large beaker of water by a thin wire. By means of the wire the bottle could be kept continuously shaken during the experiment. The beaker was slowly heated by means of a micro-burner and kept at the required temperature by adjustment of the flame. Temperatures below the room temperature were obtained by circulating water from melting ice. Experiments were conducted at different temperatures of saturation T_s , and temperatures were raised above this a number of times and allowed to fall slowly, all the while the solution in the bulb was kept shaking. At T_c there was a shower of crystals throughout the solution as described by Miers and Issac (*loc. cit.*).

This observation of the shower of crystals could be repeated any number of times with the same solution, alternately heating and cooling or with a fresh solution. The temperature was measured by means of a thermometer reading up to 0.1°. The data under each set of conditions were thoroughly repeatable in that the shower of crystals came down in each case at temperatures differing by less than 0.5°. Before cooling, the solutions were heated to higher temperatures than T_s and were kept there for 5 to 30 minutes and allowed to cool. Table I describes the results.

DISCUSSION

The results are best discussed in relation with the solubility curves of the substances and the temperature coefficient of solubility of them at different temperatures. From the solubility curves (not shown here) three types of curves are possible ideally: (i) where the temperature coefficient of solubility is constant throughout the range, (ii) where it changes continuously, and (iii) those of the hydrates which exhibit transition temperatures between the anhydrous and the hydrated forms of the substances. Majority are mixed types of (i) and (ii). Table II gives the temperature coefficients of the molal solubility (per 1000 g. of water) of the substances under review at different temperatures. This table has been computed with the aid of the molal solubilities from the International Critical Tables. The temperature coefficient of solubility at any temperature T is calculated as:

$$\frac{S_{T+5} - S_{T-5}}{10}$$

where S_{T+5} and S_{T-5} are the molal solubilities at 5° above and below the temperature T , respectively.

TABLE II

Temperature coefficient of solubility at temperatures of Substance.

	10°.	20°.	30°.	40°.	50°.	60°.	70°.	80°.	90°.
KCl	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
KNO ₃	0.09	0.12	0.15	0.20	0.23	0.27	0.29	0.33	0.35
H ₃ BO ₃	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.10	0.14
KClO ₄	0.003	0.005	0.007	0.009	0.015	0.022	←—M. S.—→		
NH ₄ Cl	0.07	0.08	0.08	(M. S.)	0.085	(M. S.)	0.09	0.10	0.11
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ · 5H ₂ O	0.06	0.07	0.10	0.26	0.28	0.19	0.12	—	—
	←—→ 5 aq		←—→ 48.2		←—→ 2 aq		←—→ 70	←—→ S	
K ₂ SO ₄ , Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ , 24/ H ₂ O	0.006	0.008	0.011	0.018	0.03	0.03	0.07	—	—
PbAc ₂ · 3H ₂ O 6.	0.04	0.06	0.11	0.23	←—→ M. S. ←—→				

M. S. denotes meta-stable and S, anhydrous substance.

The solubility curve for KCl is straight and the temperature coefficient of solubility is constant throughout the range. The supersolubility limit, $T_s - T_c$, is constant and the heating of the solution to higher temperatures than T_s and cooling do not affect the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation. To this class of substances belong others like NaCl, KBr, KI and K₂SO₄.

The case of potassium nitrate is different. The solubility coefficient with temperature increases rapidly from 10° to 30°. Between 40° and 70° it is less rapid, and again changes to a different value. Corresponding to this behaviour, $T_s - T_c$ shows different values (A) between 10° and 30° and (B) between 40° and 70°. Similar is the behaviour of boric acid; it shows four sets of such values up to 70°. Heating to higher temperatures does not affect the value of $T_s - T_c$. The temperature coefficient of solubility of KClO₄ gradually increases from 0.003 at 10° to 0.22 at 60° and thereafter with higher temperatures no more extra solubility is known, but even the saturated solution is meta-stable. Table I shows that the values for the supersaturation limit from 20° onward is constant till 60°. Heating to higher temperatures does not affect the value. At 70° and 80° no supersaturation is maintained and $T_s - T_c$ is hardly 0.1°.

The temperature coefficient of solubility of NH₄Cl is constant between 10° and 30°. At 40° and 60° the saturated solution is itself meta-stable. After 60° the values for temperature coefficient are slightly different from those of the previous ones but constant among themselves. At 50°, where there is no metastability, the value is between those at 40° and 60°

The value of $T_s - T_c$ is 3.7 between 10° and 30° and is constant.

Heating to a higher temperature does not affect the value so long as the T_s is within 30° . But the saturated solution at 40° , if heated beyond the intermediate stable temperature, *i. e.* 50° , there is stabilisation and the value of $T_s - T_c$ is 7.8 (A_1 in Table I). Again, the value of $T_s - T_c$ is different at 50° and 60° , but constant; if the saturated solutions at these temperatures are not heated much beyond 60° , the second meta-stable state of the saturated solution, they do not show any tendency to stabilisation. Data B_1 at 50° show that stabilisation against spontaneous crystallisation could be obtained by heating above the second meta-stable region of solubility. In the normal region at and above 70° , the value of $T_s - T_c$ is again low and constant.

It is clear from the above that the region of supersaturation, $T_s - T_c$, depends on the nature of the solubility of the substance at different temperatures; and if the solubility curve exhibits a meta-stable region, heating the saturated solution above this and cooling, stabilise the solution against spontaneous crystallisation or the value of $T_s - T_c$ is increased *i. g.*, A_1 , B_1 for NH_4Cl and $PbAc_2$.

Substances like sodium thiosulphate, alum and lead acetate show again a different behaviour. These possess sufficient water of crystallisation in which their corresponding anhydrides are soluble. They all exhibit transition temperatures. On heating the saturated solutions of these substances the transformation to the less hydrated or anhydrous state may possibly proceed to some extent even before the transition temperature, where complete transformation takes place. The solution on heating therefore contains the hydrated and also the dehydrated species. There is a greater amount of anhydrous molecules than hydrated ones as one approaches the transition temperature. The anhydrous substances show a decrease in solubility with increase of temperature, which means that the anhydrous species dissolve more on cooling. Hence, considerable cooling has to be done before spontaneous crystallisation takes place. They therefore maintain high range of supersolubility. $ZnSO_4$, acetic acid, $CdSO_4$ and Na_2SO_4 are a few examples of this class of substances.